

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 5*

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) cm^{-1}	$\delta(\text{CCl}_4/\text{DMSO}-d_6)$
3a	Piperidino	80	201	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	1 615 (C=N), 1 680 (C=O)	1.4 (6H, s, CH_2-C), 2.8 (4H, s, CH_2-N), 4.4 (2H, s, C_3-H), 4.6 (2H, s, CH_2-S), 6.35 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.7–7.5 (8H, m, ArH)
3b	Morpholino	80	232	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$	1 610 (C=N), 1 655 (C=O)	δ 3.4 (4H, s, N- CH_2), 4.5 (2H, s, N- CH_2-N), 4.6 (2H, s, CH_2S), 6.4 (1H, s, C_3-H)
3c	Dimethylamino	60	212	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	1 620 (C=N), 1 680 (C=O)	δ 4.6 (2H, s, CH_2-S), 5.15 (2H, s, N- CH_2-N), 6.4 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.7–7.5 (8H, m, ArH)
3d	N-Methylanilino	75	182	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	1 605 (C=N), 1 660 (C=O)	2.9 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 4.65 (2H, s, CH_2-S), 5.35 (2H, s, N- CH_2-N), 6.4 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.8–7.5 (13H, m, ArH)
3e	Pyrrolidino	70	185	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	1 610 (C=N), 1 670 (C=O)	—
5a	6- CH_3	70	265	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$	1 670 (lactum), 1 720 (lactone)	—
5b	7- CH_3	70	282	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$	1 670, 1 730	—
5c	6- OCH_3	65	252	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4\text{S}$	1 670, 1 720	—
5d	7- OCH_3	60	246	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4\text{S}$	1 665, 1 725	—
5e	5,6-Benzo	65	263	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$	1 660, 1 720	—

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses. δ N- CH_3 and O- CH_3 protons were found to merge in the DMSO peak.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Screening of New *s*-Triazolothiadiazines

M. S. CHANDE*, B. M. KARNIK and (MS.) N. GANGULY
Department of Chemistry and Microbiology,
Institute of Science, Bombay-400 032

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THE antiparasitic activities of *s*-triazoles are well-known^{1,2}. In continuation of our studies³ on the synthesis of *s*-triazolothiadiazines, a number of new 3-substituted-6,7-diaryl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]-thiadiazines (2) have been prepared by condensing the appropriate 3-substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (1) with α -bromodeoxybenzoins⁴ following the reported procedure³. The structures of the compounds were based on elemental analysis, ir, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data. Results of their antimicrobial screening have also been reported.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer. The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra were recorded on Varian VXR-300s (300 MHz) and Bruker WH-270 (67.89 MHz) FTNMR spectrometers respectively using CDCl_3 as the solvent. The following 3-aryloxymethyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-(4*H*)-1,2,4-triazoles (1; R=Ar-O CH_2) were prepared⁴. 3-Phenoxymethyl (Ar=C₆H₅), m.p. 134°; 3-*p*-toloxymethyl (Ar=*p*-CH₃-C₆H₄), m.p. 190°;

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Sl. no.	R	R ₁	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mole. formula
1.	CH ₃	H	71	163	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ S
2.	CH ₃	CH ₃	63	174	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ S
3.	CH ₃	Cl	77	181	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ S
4.	C ₂ H ₅	H	68	138	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ S
5.	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	65	213	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ S
6.	C ₂ H ₅	Cl	77	178	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ S
7.	C ₆ H ₅	H	69	196	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ S
8.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	68	184	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ S
9.	C ₆ H ₅	Cl	74	162	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ S
10.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	72	187	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ S
11.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	69	206	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ S
12.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	Cl	75	231	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ S
13.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	75	154	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ S
14.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	70	158	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ S
15.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	Cl	81	178	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ S
16.	4'-Pyridyl	H	65	225	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₄ S
17.	4'-Pyridyl	CH ₃	61	225	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ S
18.	4'-Pyridyl	Cl	74	216	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ClN ₄ S
19.	C ₆ H ₅ O-CH ₂	H	71	132	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₄ OS
20.	C ₆ H ₅ O-CH ₂	CH ₃	68	168	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS
21.	C ₆ H ₅ O-CH ₂	Cl	76	152	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OS
22.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ O-CH ₂	H	73	185	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS
23.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ O-CH ₂	CH ₃	65	220	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ OS
24.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ O-CH ₂	Cl	71	159	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ OS
25.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ O-CH ₂	H	73	142	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OS
26.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ O-CH ₂	CH ₃	73	166	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ OS
27.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ O-CH ₂	Cl	82	193	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

3-*p*-chlorophenoxymethyl (Ar=*p*-ClC₆H₄), m.p. 138°.

3-Substituted-6,7-diaryl-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]-thiadiazines (2): Compounds (2) were prepared by the condensation of α -bromodeoxybenzoins⁴ and 1 in presence of pyridine³. The ¹H nmr spectrum of compound 2 (sl. no. 8)) showed signals at δ 2.4 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 5.5 (1H, s, 7-H) and 7.2–8.2 (14H, m, ArH). The ¹³C nmr spectrum showed signals due to 17-carbon atoms in the molecule in which the signals due to carbons (C=N) C-5, C-3 and C-2 were at 154.63, 150.95 and 142.73 ppm respectively. The methylcarbon C-1 and the methyne carbon C-4 showed signals at 10.35 and 41.10 ppm respectively. The aromatic carbons showed signals in the region 126.9–142.73 ppm.

Antimicrobial screening: Compounds 2 have been found to possess considerable antimicrobial activity when tested, against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhosa*, *Salmonella para A.*, *Candida albicans* and *Serratia marscesen* using ditch-plate technique⁵. The compounds containing substituted phenyl group in the 3-position

were generally less active than those having the same substituents at the 6-position. In addition, the compounds containing 4-chloro substituents exhibited highest activity in comparison to the non-substituted ones. The tolyl derivatives showed no activity when compared with the phenyl derivatives. The equipotency of the products containing 4-pyridyl and phenyl functions can be attributed to the isostericity of both the functional groups.

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